

Prognostic Factors in Laryngeal Squamous Cell Carcinoma Treated with Curative Radiotherapy: A Retrospective Study

Radyoterapi Yapılan Larenks Kanserli Hastalarda Prognostik Faktörlerin Retrospektif Değerlendirilmesi

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To evaluate overall survival, event-free survival, and prognostic clinicopathological factors in patients with laryngeal squamous cell carcinoma treated with definitive or postoperative curative-intent radiotherapy.

Material and Method: This retrospective study included 95 patients with laryngeal squamous cell carcinoma treated with curative-intent radiotherapy. Overall survival (OS) and event-free survival (EFS) were analyzed using the Kaplan-Meier method. Restricted mean survival time (RMST) values were calculated at 24 and 60 months. Factors associated with survival were evaluated using the log-rank test, and variables with $p < 0.10$ in log-rank analysis together with clinically relevant treatment-related variables were considered for inclusion in the multivariable Cox regression model. Parsimonious models were preferred because of the limited sample size.

Results: Median follow-up was 56.7 months by the reverse Kaplan-Meier method. During follow-up, 43 deaths and 48 EFS events were observed. Median OS was 69.2 months (95% CI, 50.3-88.1), and the 2- and 5-year OS rates were 71.2% and 55.8%, respectively. Median EFS was 59.6 months (95% CI, 27.9-91.3), with 2- and 5-year EFS rates of 60.2% and 48.4%, respectively. In log-rank analyses, lymph node involvement was significantly associated with worse OS and EFS. Anterior commissure involvement was significantly associated with shorter EFS, while tumor differentiation was associated with OS. In multivariable Cox regression analysis, lymph node involvement remained an independent prognostic factor for both OS and EFS, whereas anterior commissure involvement remained independently associated with EFS.

Conclusion: Lymph node involvement was the main prognostic factor for both OS and EFS in patients with laryngeal squamous cell carcinoma treated with curative-intent radiotherapy. Anterior commissure involvement was also associated with event risk and may be useful in follow-up planning.

Keywords: Laryngeal cancer, radiotherapy, overall survival, event-free survival, prognostic factors

ÖZ

Amaç: Küratif amaçlı radyoterapi ile tedavi edilen larenks skuamöz hücreli karsinomlu hastalarda genel sağkalım (OS), olaysız sağkalım (EFS) ve prognostik klinikopatolojik faktörleri değerlendirmek.

Gereç ve Yöntem: Bu retrospektif çalışmaya küratif amaçlı radyoterapi uygulanan 95 larenks skuamöz hücreli karsinom hastası dahil edildi. OS ve EFS Kaplan-Meier yöntemi ile analiz edildi. 24 ve 60 ay için kısıtlı ortalama sağkalım süresi (RMST) hesaplandı. Sağkalım ile ilişkili faktörler log-rank testi ile değerlendirildi; log-rank analizinde $p < 0.10$ bulunan değişkenler ile klinik olarak anlamlı tedavi ilişkili değişkenler çok değişkenli Cox regresyon modeli için değerlendirildi. Sınırlı örneklem büyüklüğü nedeniyle parsimonious modeller tercih edildi.

Bulgular: Ters Kaplan-Meier yöntemi ile medyan takip süresi 56,7 ay olarak bulundu. Takip süresince 43 ölüm ve 48 EFS olayı gözlemlendi. Medyan OS 69,2 ay (%95 GA, 50,3-88,1) olup 2 ve 5 yıllık OS oranları sırasıyla %71,2 ve %55,8 idi. Medyan EFS 59,6 ay (%95 GA, 27,9-91,3) olup 2 ve 5 yıllık EFS oranları sırasıyla %60,2 ve %48,4 olarak bulundu. Log-rank analizlerinde lenf nodu tutulumu daha kötü OS ve EFS ile anlamlı olarak ilişkili bulundu. Anterior komissür tutulumu anlamlı şekilde daha kısa EFS ile ilişkilidi; tümör diferansiyasyonu ise OS ile ilişkilidi. Çok değişkenli Cox regresyon analizinde lenf nodu tutulumu hem OS hem de EFS için bağımsız prognostik faktör olarak kalırken, anterior komissür tutulumu EFS ile bağımsız olarak ilişkili bulundu.

Sonuç: Küratif amaçlı radyoterapi ile tedavi edilen larenks skuamöz hücreli karsinom hastalarında lenf nodu tutulumu hem OS hem de EFS için en önemli prognostik faktör olarak belirlendi. Anterior komissür tutulumu da nüks riski ile ilişkili olup takip planlamasında dikkate alınabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Larenks kanseri, radyoterapi, genel sağkalım, olaysız sağkalım, prognostik faktörler

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INTRODUCTION

Laryngeal cancer accounts for approximately 2-3% of all malignancies worldwide, with an estimated 180,000 new cases and around 100,000 deaths reported annually, reflecting a substantial global health burden. Laryngeal squamous cell carcinoma (LSCC) is an important malignancy within the group of head and neck cancers because its anatomical location directly affects vital functions such as voice, swallowing, and breathing. The global burden of the disease remains significant, with incidence and mortality rates particularly high among men and in populations with substantial exposure to tobacco and alcohol (1). Therefore, treatment planning for laryngeal cancer requires a multidimensional approach that aims not only to achieve tumor control but also to preserve organ function and maintain the patient's quality of life (2,3). In laryngeal cancer, treatment options including surgery, radiotherapy (RT), and chemoradiotherapy (CRT) can be used either alone or in combination, depending on the stage of the disease, the location of the primary tumor, nodal status, and the patient's clinical condition. Advances in radiotherapy techniques, systemic therapies, and multidisciplinary treatment planning have further improved the feasibility of organ preservation strategies while maintaining acceptable oncologic outcomes (4).

In early-stage disease, high local control rates can often be achieved with either RT or organ-preserving surgery, whereas in locally advanced cases, concurrent CRT for organ preservation or surgery-most commonly total laryngectomy-with or without adjuvant RT/CRT remains the standard treatment approach (5). The development of the organ preservation paradigm in laryngeal cancer has largely been shaped by pivotal clinical trials. The RTOG 91-11 trial confirmed the effectiveness of concurrent chemoradiotherapy as an important organ-preserving strategy in patients with locally advanced laryngeal cancer. Subsequent studies and reviews have continued to support these findings and have established them as key components of modern treatment algorithms (4,6). However, even among patients with similar stages of disease and comparable treatment approaches, treatment response, recurrence patterns, and long-term survival outcomes may vary considerably. This heterogeneity can be partly explained by anatomical and clinical factors such as T and N stage, histological differentiation, primary tumor subsite, and anterior commissure involvement, as well as treatment-related variables including treatment continuity and the treatment modality used. Although the prognostic impact of these factors has been demonstrated in various cohorts in the literature, the results may vary across studies due to differences in stage distribution and technical infrastructure between centers (7,8). Therefore, single-center real-world data are valuable,

particularly in historical cohorts, for evaluating how prognostic relationships manifest within local clinical practice. Given this clinical heterogeneity, identifying prognostic factors that influence survival outcomes remains crucial for optimizing treatment strategies and improving patient management.

In this study, we aimed to retrospectively evaluate the effects of clinicopathological and treatment-related variables on OS and EFS in patients with LSCC treated with definitive or postoperative curative-intent radiotherapy. Additionally, log-rank and multivariable Cox regression analyses were performed to identify independent prognostic factors associated with survival outcomes.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Study Design

This study is a retrospective, single-center analysis conducted at the Department of Radiation Oncology, Faculty of Medicine, Dicle University. Patients with histopathologically confirmed laryngeal squamous cell carcinoma who received either definitive radiotherapy or postoperative radiotherapy with curative intent between November 2002 and January 2011 were retrospectively included in this study. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Dicle University Faculty of Medicine Non-Interventional Studies Ethics Committee (Meeting No: 34, Date: 26.12.2014).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Patients were required to have sufficient clinical, pathological, and treatment-related data available in their medical records for analysis. All cases were restaged according to the American Joint Committee on Cancer 2010 TNM staging system (9). Demographic, tumor-related, and treatment-related variables were retrospectively reviewed. Patients with non-squamous cell histology, those who received only palliative treatment, patients with distant metastasis at the time of diagnosis, those who had previously received radiotherapy to the head and neck region, and patients with incomplete clinical data were excluded from the study. After applying these criteria, a total of 95 patients were included in the final analysis.

Data Collection and Evaluated Parameters

Clinical and demographic data were retrospectively obtained from patient medical records, including surgical reports, pathology reports, endoscopic examination findings, radiological imaging records, and follow-up notes. The collected variables included demographic and laboratory parameters such as age, sex, and pre-treatment hemoglobin levels, as well as tumor-related characteristics including T and lymph node involvement, tumor localization, anterior

commissure involvement, and thyroid cartilage invasion. In addition, treatment-related variables—including treatment setting, margin status, perineural invasion, lymphovascular invasion, use of concurrent chemoradiotherapy, radiotherapy interruptions, total radiation dose, fractionation schedule, and overall treatment duration—were systematically recorded. For interpretative purposes, treatment setting was defined as definitive in patients who received radiotherapy without prior surgery and as postoperative in patients who underwent surgery before radiotherapy. Follow-up data were reviewed to determine the occurrence of local and regional recurrence, distant metastasis, second primary tumors, and survival status.

Radiotherapy

Radiotherapy planning was performed using two-dimensional conventional simulation techniques. Patients were positioned supine and immobilized with a thermoplastic mask. Opposed parallel lateral fields were used for early-stage glottic tumors, whereas supraclavicular fields were included in the treatment plan for supraglottic or locally advanced cases. In patients with subglottic extension, the inferior field border was extended to include the upper mediastinum. Spinal cord tolerance doses were respected and shielding was applied when necessary. Radiotherapy was delivered using a cobalt-60 unit or a 6 MV linear accelerator, five days per week, with daily fractions of 1.8-2.0 Gy. The total dose ranged from 48 to 70 Gy. Concurrent chemoradiotherapy was administered to 64 patients (67.4%) using weekly cisplatin (25-50 mg/m²). Treatment interruptions longer than five days occurred in 9.5% of patients. At the first post-treatment clinical evaluation, disease status was assessed based on clinical examination and flexible laryngoscopy findings. No clinically evident residual local disease was observed in 95.8% of patients, whereas persistent or suspicious residual findings were noted in 4.2%. These events were not mutually exclusive; for EFS analysis, the time to the first event was considered.

Follow-up and Survival Definitions

Patients were evaluated weekly during treatment for treatment response and potential adverse effects. After completion of radiotherapy, follow-up visits were scheduled every three months for the first two years, every six months until the fifth year, and annually thereafter. During follow-up, patients underwent physical examination and routine laboratory tests, and additional radiological evaluations were performed when clinically indicated. Treatment response was assessed approximately six weeks after the completion of radiotherapy. OS was defined as the time from the date of diagnosis to the date of death from any cause. Patients who were alive or lost to follow-up were censored at the date of the last clinical contact. EFS was defined as the time from diagnosis to the occurrence of

local or regional recurrence, distant metastasis, second primary tumor, or death, whichever occurred first. Patients without any of these events were censored at the date of the last follow-up.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS software version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. OS and EFS were estimated using the Kaplan–Meier method, and differences between groups were compared using the log-rank test. Median follow-up time was calculated using the reverse Kaplan–Meier method. In addition, RMST values at 24 and 60 months were calculated as complementary measures of survival. RMST reflects the average survival time within a prespecified time horizon and provides an absolute measure in months, complementing the relative estimates obtained from log-rank and Cox regression analyses. Variables with $p < 0.10$ in log-rank analysis and clinically relevant treatment-related variables were considered for inclusion in the multivariable Cox proportional hazards regression model. Because of the limited sample size, parsimonious models were preferred. Variables reflecting overlapping staging information were not entered simultaneously into the same model. Hazard ratios (HRs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were reported. All statistical tests were two-sided, and $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 95 patients were included in the analysis. The majority of the patients were male, with 88 (92.6%) males and 7 (7.4%) females. Regarding age distribution, 47 patients (48.4%) were ≤ 60 years, while 48 patients (51.6%) were > 60 years. Hemoglobin levels before treatment were ≥ 12 g/dL in 49 patients (51.6%) and < 12 g/dL in 46 patients (48.4%). According to tumor staging, 43 patients (45.3%) had T4 disease, 19 (20.0%) had T3, 19 (20.0%) had T2, and 14 (14.7%) had T1 tumors. In terms of nodal status, 67 patients (70.5%) were classified as N0, 20 (21.1%) as N1, and 8 (8.4%) as N2. The overall stage distribution showed that 46 patients (48.4%) were stage IV, 24 (25.3%) were stage III, 11 (11.6%) were stage II, and 14 (14.7%) were stage I. The most common primary tumor location was the glottic region (55.8%), followed by the supraglottic region (43.2%), while subglottic tumors were rare (1.1%). Anterior commissure involvement was observed in 44.2% of patients, and thyroid cartilage invasion in 43.2%. Histopathological evaluation revealed that 20.0% of tumors were well differentiated, 58.9% were moderately differentiated, and 21.1% were poorly differentiated. Regarding treatment setting, 48 patients (50.5%) received definitive radiotherapy-based treatment, whereas 47 patients (49.5%) received postoperative radiotherapy-based treatment. Among the 47 patients

who underwent surgery, the most frequently performed surgical procedure was total laryngectomy (40, 85.1%), followed by partial laryngectomy (7, 14.9%). Among the 47 patients who underwent surgery, neck dissection was performed in 42 (89.4%); of these, 26 patients underwent bilateral neck dissection (**Table 1**).

Table 1. Demographic, tumor, and treatment characteristics of the study population (n = 95)

Demographic Characteristics	n (%)
Age (year)	
≤60	47 (48.4)
>60	48 (51.6)
Hemoglobin level (g/dL)	
≥12	49 (51.6)
<12	46 (48.4)
Gender	
Male	88 (92.6)
Female	7 (7.4)
Tumor Staging (AJCC 2010)	
T1	14 (14.7)
T2	19 (20.0)
T3	19 (20.0)
T4	43 (45.3)
N0	67 (70.5)
N1	20 (21.1)
N2	8 (8.4)
Stage I	14 (14.7)
Stage II	11 (11.6)
Stage III	24 (25.3)
Stage IV	46 (48.4)
Tumor Location	
Supraglottic	41 (43.2)
Glottic	53 (55.8)
Subglottic	1 (1.1)
Anterior commissure involvement	42 (44.2)
Thyroid cartilage invasion	41 (43.2)
Tumor Differentiation	
Well differentiated	19 (20.0)
Moderately differentiated	56 (58.9)
Poorly differentiated	20 (21.1)
Pathological Characteristics (Patients Undergoing Surgery, n=47)	
Positive surgical margin	19 (40.4)
Close surgical margin	9 (19.1)
Negative surgical margin	19 (40.4)
Perineural invasion	7 (14.9)
Lymphovascular invasion	11 (23.4)
Treatment Characteristics	
Definitive radiotherapy-based treatment	48 (50.5)
Postoperative radiotherapy-based treatment	47 (49.5)
Neck dissection status among operated patients (n = 47)	
Neck dissection performed	42(89.4)
No neck dissection	5(10.6)
Surgery Type Among Operated Patients (n = 47)	
Total laryngectomy	40 (85.1)
Partial laryngectomy	7 (14.9)

Percentages for treatment setting were calculated for the overall cohort (n = 95). Percentages for surgery type and neck dissection status were calculated among operated patients (n = 47).

EFS and OS were evaluated according to clinicopathological variables using the Kaplan–Meier method, and RMST values were calculated at 24 and 60 months. No statistically significant differences in EFS or OS were found with respect to age, sex, hemoglobin level, tumor stage, overall stage, tumor location, thyroid cartilage invasion, treatment setting, surgical margin status, perineural invasion, lymphovascular invasion, concurrent chemoradiotherapy, or treatment interruption longer than 5 days. Although patients with lower tumor stage (T1-T2) and earlier disease stage (stage I-II) tended to have better survival outcomes than those with more advanced disease, these differences were not statistically significant. By contrast, lymph node involvement was associated with lower survival times and was significantly associated with both EFS ($p=0.007$) and OS ($p=0.002$). Tumor differentiation was not significantly associated with EFS ($p=0.38$), but it was significantly associated with OS ($p=0.036$). Anterior commissure involvement was also significantly associated with shorter EFS ($p=0.008$), whereas no significant relationship was observed with OS ($p=0.234$). In summary, lymph node involvement and anterior commissure involvement were the main variables associated with EFS, while lymph node involvement and tumor differentiation were associated with OS in unadjusted analyses. RMST analysis also provided an absolute estimate of survival loss within clinically relevant time windows. Node-positive patients had fewer EFS months than node-negative patients at both 24 and 60 months (4.17 and 13.13 months, respectively), with corresponding OS losses of 4.60 and 15.90 months. Anterior commissure involvement was likewise associated with shorter EFS at 24 and 60 months (3.53 and 11.91 months, respectively). These findings supported the clinical relevance of the survival differences observed in the Kaplan-Meier analyses (**Table 2**).

In multivariable Cox regression analysis for OS, lymph node involvement remained an independent adverse prognostic factor (HR: 2.783, 95% CI: 1.385-5.591, $p=0.004$). Treatment setting (HR: 0.741, 95% CI: 0.375-1.466, $p=0.389$), concurrent chemoradiotherapy (HR: 1.163, 95% CI: 0.599-2.259, $p=0.656$), and tumor differentiation (overall $p=0.464$) were not independently associated with OS. In multivariable analysis for EFS, lymph node involvement (HR: 2.413, 95% CI: 1.257-4.63, $p=0.008$) and anterior commissure involvement (HR: 2.2, 95% CI: 1.212-3.993, $p=0.010$) remained independent prognostic factors, whereas treatment setting (HR: 0.821, 95% CI: 0.443-1.522, $p=0.531$) and concurrent chemoradiotherapy (HR: 1.119, 95% CI: 0.586-2.134, $p=0.734$) were not significantly associated with EFS (**Table 3**).

Table 2. Event-free survival (EFS) and overall survival (OS) analyses according to clinicopathological variables using restricted mean survival time (RMST) at 24 and 60 months (Kaplan–Meier method).

	EFS RMST (24 months)	EFS RMST (60 months)	EFS p value	OS RMST (24 months)	OS RMST (60 months)	OS p value
Age (year)			0.85			0.97
≤60	18.06	36.03		19.78	42.02	
>60	18.32	38.53		19.97	43.34	
Gender			0.27			0.14
Male	18.37	37.89		20.15	43.38	
Female	16.52	32.16		16.96	36.40	
Hemoglobin level (g/dL)			0.32			0.25
≥12	18.46	39.59		19.19	41.75	
<12	18.13	35.49		20.63	44.04	
Tumor Staging			0.25			0.25
T1-T2	19.34	42.30		21.93	48.06	
T3-T4	17.97	36.55		18.81	39.96	
Lymph Node Involvement			0.007			0.002
Negative	19.46	41.23		21.30	47.50	
Positive	15.29	28.10		16.7	31.60	
Stage			0.16			0.17
I-II	20.93	44.34		22.58	50.26	
III-IV	17.26	34.97		18.93	40.04	
Differentiation			0.38			0.036
Well	19.39	42.93		22.90	56.65	
Moderate	17.74	36.49		20.77	44.97	
Poor	18.50	34.08		20.66	39.61	
Tumor Location			0.25			0.12
Glottic	19.06	39.36		21.31	46.86	
Non-glottic	17.14	34.90		18.11	37.54	
Anterior commissure involvement			0.008			0.234
No	19.79	42.76		21.6	47.1	
Yes	16.26	30.85		20.1	43.5	
Thyroid Cartilage Invasion			0.11			0.14
No	19.85	41.62		21.06	46.44	
Yes	16.05	31.92		18.33	37.81	
Treatment setting			0.86			0.77
Definitive	18.56	35.68		19.64	40.17	
Postoperative	18.67	38.14		18.55	39.98	
Surgical Margin			0.25			0.1
Negative	16.99	33.71		20.08	42.80	
Close	14.29	27.79		15.30	28.80	
Positive	20.36	44.98		21.51	47.93	
Perineural Invasion			0.30			0.70
Negative	17.72	38.62		20.00	42.61	
Positive	9.91	26.49		18.74	42.17	
Lymphovascular Invasion			0.11			0.28
Negative	18.01	39.82		20.40	44.70	
Positive	10.98	30.32		17.55	33.99	
Concurrent Chemoradiotherapy			0.65			0.85
No	19.38	39.04		21.15	44.39	
Yes	17.67	36.67		19.32	42.06	
Treatment Interruption			0.44			0.89
≤5 days	18.56	37.95		19.64	42.04	
>5 days	15.43	33.43		21.98	48.91	

Survival outcomes were estimated using the Kaplan-Meier method. RMST values at 24 and 60 months are presented to show the average survival time accumulated within fixed follow-up horizons and to facilitate absolute between-group comparisons in months. P values were derived from log-rank tests and are provided separately from RMST estimates.

Table 3. Multivariable Cox regression analysis for overall survival and event-free survival

Outcome	Variable	Hazard Ratio (HR)	95% CI	p value
Overall Survival	Lymph Node Involvement	2.783	1.385 – 5.591	0.004
	Tumor differentiation (overall)	—	—	0.464
	Moderate vs well Differentiation	1.741	0.724 – 4.190	0.216
	Poor vs well Differentiation	1.646	0.534 – 5.071	0.385
	Treatment setting (postoperative vs definitive)	0.741	0.375–1.466	0.389
Event-Free Survival	Concurrent chemoradiotherapy	1.163	0.599–2.259	0.656
	Lymph Node Involvement	2.413	1.257–4.63	0.008
	Anterior Commissure Involvement	2.200	1.212–3.993	0.010
	Treatment setting (postoperative vs definitive)	0.821	0.443–1.522	0.531
	Concurrent chemoradiotherapy	1.119	0.586–2.134	0.734

HR: hazard ratio; CI: confidence interval. Variables with p<0.10 in log-rank analysis and clinically relevant treatment-related variables were considered for the multivariable Cox proportional hazards model. Because of the limited sample size, parsimonious models were preferred. The reference category for tumor differentiation was well differentiated.

Figure 1. Kaplan–Meier curves for EFS and OS in the study cohort.

Follow-up and Survival Outcomes

Median follow-up was estimated using the reverse Kaplan-Meier method and was found to be 56.7 months. In the OS analysis, 43 deaths were recorded, and 52 patients were censored. The median OS was 69.2 months (95% CI, 50.3–88.1), with 2-year and 5-year OS rates of 71.2% and 55.8%, respectively. In the EFS analysis, 48 events were observed, while 47 patients were censored. The median EFS was 59.6 months (95% CI, 27.9–91.3), and the 2-year and 5-year EFS rates were 60.2% and 48.4%, respectively (**Figure 1**).

DISCUSSION

In the present study, we evaluated clinicopathological factors influencing survival in patients with laryngeal squamous cell carcinoma treated with curative radiotherapy, and lymph node involvement emerged as the strongest prognostic determinant for both OS and

EFS. In the multivariable Cox regression analysis, lymph node involvement remained an independent prognostic factor for both survival outcomes, further supporting the well-established role of cervical nodal metastasis as a key indicator of tumor aggressiveness in laryngeal cancer. Previous studies have similarly reported that the presence of nodal disease adversely affects both local control and long-term survival outcomes.

In a comprehensive review, Steuer et al. emphasized that nodal involvement represents one of the most important prognostic factors in head and neck squamous cell carcinomas (6). Lymph node involvement was significantly associated with both EFS and OS in the log-rank analysis. RMST analysis also demonstrated a clinically meaningful reduction in survival time among node-positive patients. At 60 months, node-positive patients had 13.13 fewer EFS months and 15.90 fewer OS months than node-negative patients. Thus, RMST complemented the log-rank and Cox analyses by

providing an absolute measure of survival loss, while the multivariable model confirmed the independent adverse prognostic effect of nodal involvement. Similarly, Grover et al. reported significantly worse OS and EFS in patients with nodal metastases, emphasizing the importance of regional disease burden (8). Consistent with our results, Bernasconi et al. reported that increased nodal tumor volume and lymph node involvement are strongly associated with poorer survival outcomes in patients with oral and head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (10). Similarly, Pelaz et al. highlighted that cervical lymph node metastasis remains one of the most important determinants of prognosis in these tumors (11). Although T stage and overall stage were not significantly associated with OS or EFS, lower-stage groups showed numerically better survival. This lack of statistical significance may be related to the limited sample size, the predominance of advanced-stage cases, treatment heterogeneity, and the use of diagnosis date as the starting point for survival analyses. Another notable finding of our study was that anterior commissure involvement emerged as an independent prognostic factor for EFS. Its significance in the log-rank analysis and multivariable model suggests that the anterior commissure may represent a clinically relevant laryngeal subsite influencing local tumor behavior. This observation may be explained by the complex anatomy of the anterior commissure and its close relationship with the thyroid cartilage. In particular, the absence of the inner perichondrium in this region has been proposed as a potential pathway for submucosal tumor extension.

Anterior commissure involvement has been regarded as a potentially unfavorable feature in laryngeal cancer because of its anatomical characteristics, which may facilitate submucosal spread and extension to adjacent structures, thereby increasing the risk of local persistence or recurrence (12). Evidence from a systematic review, meta-analysis, and clinical series suggests that its adverse prognostic effect is observed more consistently in local control and recurrence-related outcomes than in OS (12–14). Although most published data are derived from early-stage glottic tumors, our findings are broadly consistent with this pattern. In the present study, anterior commissure involvement was associated with EFS rather than OS, suggesting that its prognostic relevance may be driven primarily by recurrence-related events (15). Similarly, anterior commissure involvement was associated with an approximately 11.9-month reduction in EFS at 60 months, supporting the clinical relevance of this finding. Tumor differentiation was associated with OS in the log-rank analysis in our study; however, this association was not maintained in the multivariable model. In the literature, poorly differentiated tumors have often been reported to exhibit more aggressive biological behavior

and to be associated with poorer outcomes (16). However, this finding may reflect confounding by other clinicopathological factors that were more strongly associated with survival in our cohort, particularly lymph node involvement. In addition, the limited sample size and the relatively small numbers in some differentiation subgroups may have reduced the precision of the adjusted estimates. Therefore, tumor differentiation may be associated with outcome in unadjusted analyses without remaining an independent prognostic factor after multivariable adjustment. In contrast, nodal disease burden has consistently been identified as a major determinant of survival outcomes in laryngeal cancer (17). Consequently, in several studies the significance observed in initial log-rank analyses has not been maintained in multivariable models. In the surgical subgroup, perineural invasion, lymphovascular invasion, and surgical margin status were not significantly associated with survival outcomes. The findings related to surgical margin status should be interpreted cautiously. The relatively small surgical subgroup and the limited number of patients in each margin category may have reduced statistical power and contributed to unstable results. In addition, because margin status was evaluated only in operated patients, selection bias cannot be excluded, and postoperative radiotherapy may have attenuated the observable effect of margin status on survival. However, these analyses were limited to the 47 patients who underwent surgery, resulting in a relatively small subgroup and reduced statistical power. Therefore, conclusions regarding these surgical-pathological variables should be interpreted cautiously, and the lack of statistical significance should not be considered definitive evidence that these factors have no prognostic relevance.

Previous studies have suggested that both perineural and lymphovascular invasion may be associated with poorer survival outcomes in head and neck cancers. Similarly, Krishnamurthy S et al. indicated that lymphovascular invasion may also be related to unfavorable prognostic outcomes. However, the prognostic significance of these factors can vary depending on tumor stage, treatment modality, and characteristics of the patient population (18). Overall, the findings of the present study further support the prognostic importance of nodal status in laryngeal cancer. In addition, anterior commissure involvement may represent a potential prognostic indicator, particularly for EFS. These observations highlight the importance of careful assessment of nodal status in treatment planning and follow-up strategies. Moreover, patients with anterior commissure involvement may require closer surveillance because of a potentially higher risk of recurrence-related events. Future studies with larger patient populations and preferably multicenter designs are needed to further clarify these associations.

The main limitations of this study include its retrospective design, single-center data, small sample sizes in some subgroups (very low *n* in certain categories), heterogeneity in treatment approaches (definitive vs. postoperative/adjuvant radiotherapy and concurrent chemoradiotherapy), and the possibility of missing data for some variables. To improve interpretability, treatment setting was also considered as definitive or postoperative according to whether radiotherapy was delivered without or after surgery; however, the mixed treatment context of the cohort should still be taken into account when interpreting the survival findings. In addition, survival outcomes were calculated from the date of diagnosis; because the cohort included both patients treated with definitive radiotherapy and those receiving postoperative radiotherapy, the interval between diagnosis and initiation of radiotherapy may have varied across patients, potentially introducing additional heterogeneity into the survival analyses. Moreover, the use of conventional two-dimensional radiotherapy techniques reflects the historical treatment period of this cohort. Compared with modern techniques such as IMRT, two-dimensional radiotherapy provides less conformal target coverage and more limited sparing of surrounding normal tissues, which may affect local control, treatment-related toxicity, and treatment continuity. Therefore, the absolute survival outcomes observed in this study should not be directly generalized to current radiotherapy practice. Accordingly, survival estimates, particularly in small subgroups, should be interpreted with caution. Despite these limitations, the study has several strengths. All patients were evaluated within a single center, and clinicopathological variables were analyzed using multivariable statistical models. In addition, the use of real-world clinical data provides findings that may contribute to clinical practice.

CONCLUSION

Lymph node involvement was identified as an independent prognostic factor for both OS and EFS in patients with laryngeal squamous cell carcinoma treated with curative-intent radiotherapy. In addition, anterior commissure involvement emerged as an independent prognostic factor for EFS. These findings suggest that both lymph node status and anterior commissure involvement should be carefully considered in prognostic assessment, treatment planning, and follow-up strategies. In particular, patients with anterior commissure involvement may require closer surveillance because of a potentially higher risk of events. However, given the retrospective nature of the study, its single-center design, and treatment heterogeneity, larger prospective multicenter studies are needed to confirm these findings.

ETHICAL DECLARATIONS

Ethics Committee Approval: This study was approved by the Dicle University Faculty of Medicine Non-Interventional Studies Ethics Committee (Meeting No: 34, Date: 26.12.2014).

Informed Consent: Informed consent is not required for this study.

Referee Evaluation Process: Externally peer-reviewed.

Conflict of Interest Statement: The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Use of Artificial Intelligence: Artificial intelligence tools were used only for language editing during manuscript preparation and were not used for data generation, analysis, or scientific interpretation.

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